

Legacy of Priyadarajan Ray towards Artificial Photosynthesis[#]

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It is with great humbleness that I accept this honour of delivering the Professor Priyadarajan Ray Memorial Lecture. It was by a coincidence that twentyfive years ago while doing a literature survey for the topic of my Ph.D. dissertation I had almost decided to work on the problem of metal complexes of rubeanic acid (i.e. dithioamide) due to the comprehensive account of this ligand and its metallic derivatives provided by Acharya Ray¹. However, the lure of biologically relevant ligands led me to choose another topic dealing with hydroxynaphthoquinone ligands. In 1984 during my Fulbright year at the University of Illinois while I was trying to learn the basics of an interface area between biology and chemistry, viz. photosynthesis, in the laboratories of Professor David Hendrickson and Professor Govindjee I again came across an unusually interesting account of higher valent manganese compounds stabilised by biguanide ligands^{2,3}. The account was a total surprise for us because : (i) the importance of dimeric or tetrameric manganese complexes was only beginning to be realised as the relevant models for mimicking the water oxidising complex (WOC) of photosystem II, (ii) very few papers were available at the time from the Indian scientists providing account of higher valent manganese compounds, (iii) curiously the two papers by Acharya Ray described dimeric complexes containing Mn in +3 and +4 oxidation states and it even provided the variable temperature magnetic susceptibility data on these compounds upto 140 K and (iv) the proposed structure for these dimeric compounds included hydroxyl bridges which were thought to be essential intermediates in the oxidation of water molecules to molecular oxygen. I must

say that the account provided me with great inspiration and inner strength to undertake work on the manganese model compounds which not only can provide structural models of the WOC but also as the functional models capable of performing the same task as do the native compounds. The present article is intended to provide a brief account of our efforts in this direction over the past ten years.

What do we know about WOC in photosystem II

The process of photosynthetic water cleavage involves oxidation of two water molecules to dioxygen and 4 photons,

and requires two indispensable pre-requisites : (a) the generation of sufficiently oxidising redox equivalents and (b) the cooperation and accumulation of four oxidation equivalents. The first requirement is achieved by light-induced electron ejection from the lowest excited singlet state of a special chlorophyll a species (designates as P₆₈₀) with pheophytin (Pheo) as primary acceptor followed by a transfer of electron to the special plastoquinone, Q_A⁴. The second requirement is fulfilled via a sequence of univalent electron abstraction steps in the catalytic cycle commonly referred as the Kok's cycle⁵ from a manganese containing unit, the water oxidising complex (WOC). Oxygen is released after the accumulation of four oxidation equivalents within the WOC. The redox components participating in the process of water oxidation are incorporated into an integral membrane protein complex referred to as photosystem II (PS II) which is anisotropically

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incorporated into the thylakoid membrane and associated with extrinsic regulatory subunits (Fig. 1)⁶.

Fig. 1. A diagrammatic representation of the photosystem II (PS II) complex embedded in the thylakoid membrane of the chloroplast. Abbreviations used: P680 = primary electron donor; Pheo = pheophytin; QA and QB = secondary electron acceptor quinones; Z and D = tyrosine residues which are oxidised by P680; D1, D2, CP-43, CP-47 and Cyt b-559 are the associated polypeptides; MSP = manganese stabilising protein.

Although significant progress has been achieved in understanding the photosynthetic water oxidation, especially with respect to kinetic pattern⁷, the key mechanistic questions still remain to be answered^{8,9}. Similarly, the structure of the water oxidising enzyme, the nature of its protein matrix and the role of essential cofactors such as Ca and Cl ions are not yet resolved. On the whole it now seems clear that a functionally competent WOC contains 4 Mn atoms¹⁰ while several lines of evidences indicate that these 4 Mn centers are likely not to be functionally equivalent^{8,9}. According to some workers only 2 Mn are inferred to be indispensable for the oxidative pathway leading to water oxidation, while the other two are reported to be replacable under certain conditions by other divalent cations and probably play a structural role^{11,12}. The idea of manganese heterogeneity within the WOC was proposed on the basis of selective population of the 'superreduced' states S₋₁ and S₋₂ which has gained

further support from EXAFS data¹³. The EXAFS results can be consistently explained by a 'dimer of dimer' model and a scheme representing the most likely distribution of the oxidation steps on such tetranuclear cluster according to Kok's catalytic cycle (Fig. 2)

S ₀	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄
Mn ^{II} , Mn ^{III}	Mn ^{III} ₂	Mn ^{III}	Mn ^{III}	?
Mn ^{IV} ₂	Mn ^{IV} ₂	Mn ^{IV} ₃	Mn ^{IV} ₃	
			org radical	
			Mn ^{IV} ₄	

Fig. 2. S-state model of photosynthetic water oxidation according to Kok *et al.* and a speculative scheme of the redox states of Mn during the catalytic cycle.

has recently been published¹⁴. EXAFS studies have also indicated that the Mn-Mn distances in the dimeric units of WOC are 2.7 and 3.3 Å respectively, and that only N,O-donor atoms constitute the first coordination sphere of manganese ions¹⁵.

Model compounds of WOC

Based on the spectroscopic, magnetic and structural information available on the native WOC a large number of coordination compounds containing Mn in different oxidation states have been synthesised and characterised^{16,17}. Major types among the X-ray characterised compounds include the adamantane, cubane and butterfly type of frameworks (Fig. 3) reported by Brudvig and Crabtree¹⁸ and Vincent

Fig 3. Major hypothetical structural types suggested for the Mn cluster involved in water oxidation : (a) adamantane; (b) distorted cubane and (c) distorted butterfly.

and Christou¹⁹. However, the EXAFS data on PS II do not correlate well with any of these model compounds. EXAFS studies on PS II have indicated that Mn ions at WOC site are predominantly coordinated to oxygen donor ligands (oxo and carboxylato groups) with few nitrogen compounds (histidine groups)^{14,15}. The unambiguous Mn...Mn distance of 2.7 Å is typical of di- μ -oxo-dimanganese compounds while the less certain distance of 3.3 Å is typical of that found in dinuclear μ -oxo-bis(μ -carboxylato) dimanganese complexes. A combination of these two structural types leads logically to the Berkeley model suggested recently (Fig. 4). It may also be noted that none of the characterised compounds has actually been shown to be functional in processing the natural substrates or their analogs.

Work in our laboratory

Work on photosynthesis was initiated in our laboratory as a result of my close affiliation with Professor Govindjee at University of Illinois during 1984-85 by proposing a manganese histidine cluster as the model of functional center of WOC in PS II²⁰. In this model, the role of electron mediation between WOC and Z was attributed to the histidine moiety which has now been confirmed by French²¹ and Japanese²² researchers. The involvement of histidine residues in the electron transport has recently

Fig 4. Schematic representation of the Berkeley model of the water oxidising enzyme.

been examined by us after chemically modifying the histidine residues of PS II in isolated spinach thylakoids by diethylpyrocarbonate treatment and following the electron recombinations by thermoluminescence technique²³. This work revealed that histidines seem to play a crucial role in the electron transport on both the donor and acceptor sides of PS II. Using a dynamic Mössbauer spectroscopic technique we had shown that the non-heme iron at the acceptor side of PS II can undergo valence changes upon illumination on the scale of about 8 μ s²⁴. By refinement and modification of the same technique it may be possible in future to examine the role of histidines in the electron mediation between Q_A and Q_B .

For constructing the biomimetic models of the manganese co-factor involved in water oxidation in PS II we have adopted the use of redox-active ligands like quinones or catechols for stabilisation of different oxidation states of Mn. The combination of transition metal ions with such redox-active ligands allows one to modulate the closely proximated energy levels of the resulting complexes such that metal to ligand electron transfers become easily possible. The reaction pathways for such electron transfers are often achieved through dimeric or tetrameric association. For example, in the manganese complex arising out of the interaction of manganese complex of a hydroxynaphthoquinone ligand of natural occurrence (viz. lawsone) with 1.10-phenanthroline the two Mn^{2+} centers are bridged by the quinone ligands (Fig. 5)²⁵. The Mn ions in this compound are heptacoordinated with a donor atom set of N_2O_5 and Mn-Mn distance of 3.626 Å. A similar situation

Fig. 5. 1,10-Phenanthroline adduct of lawsone (2-hydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone), the coloring pigment of henna.

is also observed in case of lawsonemonooxime complex of Mn(III,III) species although in this compound the charge transfer is probably achieved through oxo- and carboxylato-bridges²⁶. It has already been pointed out earlier that compounds containing such mixed bridges contain Mn...Mn distances of 2.7 and 3.3 Å respectively, both of which are supported by EXAFS data on PS II and these compounds, therefore, offer as excellent materials for reconstititional studies^{27,28}.

The cavity former hydroxamic acid ligands prompted us to re-examine the crystal structure of Mn-salicyladoxime compound. The compound indeed exhibited a [9-crown-3] arrangement of the three manganese atoms (Fig. 6) with average Mn-O, Mn-N and Mn-Mn distances of 2.259, 2.248 and 3.559 Å respectively²⁹.

Recently we started looking at the process of photoassembly of Mn cluster more closely and decided to employ a catecholimine system of ligands with histidine arms for creating the manganese cluster assembly³⁰. This ligating system has yielded a series of tetranuclear compounds involving many of the first row transition metal ions. The tetranuclear manganese compound has a near-linear arrangement (Fig. 7) with Mn...Mn distances of 3.297 and 3.413 Å respectively³¹. The system is quite interesting because it contains a pair of Mn dimers bridged by di-oxo

Fig. 6. Manganese tetramer of salicyladoxime.

Fig. 7. Manganese tetramer of catecholimine ligand wherein the inner pair of manganese atoms which hold two water molecules are coupled together by two catechol oxygens while the outer pairs are bridged by two carboxylate groups and a π -oxo linkage

bridges provided by one of the catechol oxygens. In addition it also contains the dicarboxylato bridges involving the outer pair of manganese ions. The most important structural feature of this tetramer is the two solvent molecules (replacable by water) held in a *cis* manner adjacently by the inner pair of manganese ions. The broad features of this compound are closely matching with those of the Berkley model.

Most interesting experiments have been performed on these tetranuclear Mn compounds recently which involved the reconstitution studies on the oxygen evolution capacity of PS II preparations lacking a functionally competent WOC. The results of these experiments reveal that these tetranuclear complexes

Fig. 8 Rates of oxygen evolution from NH₂OH-washed PS II preparations of spinach before (a) and after photoactivation with synthetic Mn₄ cluster at concentration 0.2 mM for 8 mins (b) and 25 mins (c).

are highly efficient PS II electron donors and powerful substances for establishing inside the protein matrix a manganese cluster that is fully competent for photosynthetic water oxidation. Fig. 8a shows the complete inhibition of oxygen evolution by hydroxylamine treatment to the PS II particles from spinach and restoration of the O₂ evolution activity upon reconstitution and photoreactivation (Figs. 8b, c) with the above tetranuclear Mn complex.

Finally, the photoactivated PS II preparations from spinach with the tetranuclear species were illuminated at 200 K to determine the difference epr spectrum, i.e. light minus dark spectrum. Such a spectrum (Fig. 9) shows a broad signal centered at approximately $g = 4$ while a series of about 5 to 6 lines each separated by about 260 gauss is also visible above 380 mT. More lines may be present in this spectrum but these are obscured by the Fe-Q_A signal and the six-line signal originating probably from the oxidised cluster. It indicates that precautions are necessary during photoactivation experiments to avoid oxidations. It may perhaps reflect the additional role played by the water-soluble external polypeptides in protecting the WOC from such oxidations. A comparison of these spectra with the illumination changes at 200 K in the native PS II preparations (inset in Fig. 9) indicates that the reaction centers in which the above synthetic cluster is incorporated

Fig. 9. Light minus dark epr spectrum of photoreactivated PS II preparation from spinach subchloroplasts with catecholimine Mn₄ cluster at 200 K. The inset shows the dark adapted, illuminated and light minus dark epr spectra of the native enzyme in the presence of 40 μM DCMU.

undergo similar structural changes during photoreactivation as the native compound. Detailed experiments are presently in progress to analyse this process.

In summary, our work on biomimetic models of water oxidase enzyme has shown that well-designed synthetic manganese complexes can provide as invaluable complimentary tools for analysing the assembly of WOC and may bring us closer to realising the long-term goal of achieving artificial photosynthesis to harness solar energy at affordable price.

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